

Kinetic Investigations of Positive Halogen Reactions. Oxidation of Semicarbazide by Chloramine-T and Dichloramine-T

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Kinetics of oxidation of semicarbazide (SC) by chloramine-T (CAT) in aqueous perchloric acid medium and dichloramine-T (DCT) in 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol medium have been studied. Oxidation of semicarbazide by CAT and DCT followed the rate laws,

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = [\text{CAT}]^2 \{k + k'[\text{H}^+]\} \quad \text{and} \quad -\frac{d[\text{DCT}]}{dt} = \frac{k''[\text{DCT}][\text{H}^+]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]}$$

respectively.

Effects of addition of reaction product and variations in ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium have also been investigated. Mechanisms in accord with the observed rate laws are discussed.

THE chemistry of thiosemicarbazide (TSC), its derivatives and oxygen homologue, semicarbazide (SC) has attracted the attention of many investigators due to their biological activity and synthetic applications¹⁻³. They are very good metal chelating agents and their reactions with various metal ions in solution have been studied in relation to their bonding and structures¹⁻⁴. Aldehydes and ketones condense readily with both thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide to give the corresponding carbazones^{1,2}. In addition to their crystallinity, it is the acid stability of hydrazones which led to their popularity for characterisation of aldehydes, ketones and polysaccharides.

The chemistry of *N*-halo-*N*-metallo and *N,N*-dihaloaromatic sulphonamides has also evinced considerable interest due to their diverse behaviour and greater stability compared to hypohalites⁵. In our laboratories we have extensively employed them for determining a variety of substrates in solution⁶. We have also studied the mechanistic aspects of some of these reactions⁷. The present investigation is a part of our kinetic and mechanistic studies with positive halogens in general and *N*-halo-*N*-metallo aromatic sulphonamides in particular. We report herein the kinetics of oxidation of semicarbazide by chloramine-T in aqueous perchloric acid medium and dichloramine-T in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol.

Experimental

Chloramine-T (CAT) (Fluka, AG) was purified by the method reported elsewhere. Dichloramine-T (DCT) was prepared by the chlorination of aqueous CAT solution⁸. The purity of the oxidants was

checked by recording their ir and nmr spectra and by iodometric estimation of the amount of positive halogen present in them. DCT is insoluble in water but soluble in acetic acid and alcohols. Stock solutions (~0.1 mol dm⁻³) of the oxidants, CAT in water and DCT in methanol and the substrate, semicarbazide hydrochloride (SC) (Loba, AR) in water were prepared, standardised and stored in dark-coloured bottles.

Ionic strength of the reaction medium was kept at 0.3 mol dm⁻³ with sodium perchlorate (E. Merck). All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The acid strength due to hydrochloride was taken into account while maintaining overall [H⁺] and [Cl⁻].

Kinetic measurements : The kinetic studies were made in glass-stoppered (Pyrex) boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [SC] >> [oxidant] (5-20 fold excess). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution (0.00025-0.004 mol dm⁻³) thermally equilibrated at a desired temperature, to a solution containing known amounts of SC (0.005-0.10 mol dm⁻³), perchloric acid (0.002-0.04 mol dm⁻³), sodium perchlorate and water (and methanol with DCT to maintain 1 : 1 (v/v) solvent composition), pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions were monitored for two half-lives by the iodometric method. The rate constants were computed by the method of least-squares and were reproducible within ±3%.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Stoichiometries of SC-CAT and SC-DCT reactions were determined by allowing the reactions to go to completion at different [H⁺] (0.01-0.2 mol dm⁻³)

and [substrate]/[oxidant] ratios. The presence of cyanate in the reaction products was detected by standard tests⁹. *p*-Toluenesulphonamide, the reduced product of the oxidant, was detected by paper chromatography employing benzyl alcohol saturated with water as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ether as the spray reagent ($R_f=0.91$). N_2 was estimated quantitatively by Schiff's nitrometer. A slow and steady current of pure and dry CO_2 was passed through the reaction vessel to sweep off N_2 . N_2 along with CO_2 was lead to the nitrometer filled with 50% KOH where CO_2 was completely absorbed. The volume of N_2 collected was noted after equalising the levels of solution in the nitrometer and reservoir to the same height. The observed stoichiometries may be represented by equation (1),

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of oxidation of semicarbazide (SC) by CAT in aqueous perchloric acid medium, and DCT in 1 : 1 aqueous methanol medium were investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants and $HClO_4$ (0.001–0.10 mol dm^{-3}) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR OXIDATION OF SEMICARBAZIDE (SC) BY CHLORAMINE-T (CAT) IN AQUEOUS PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM

Temp. = 303 K, $\mu = 0.3 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$			
[CAT] ₀ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$	[SC] ₀ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$	[HClO ₄] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$	k_{obs} $dm^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} s^{-1}$
Effect of varying [CAT] ₀			
0.5	2.0	5.0	0.59
1.0	2.0	5.0	0.61
2.0	2.0	5.0	0.60
4.0	2.0	5.0	0.62
Effect of varying [SC] ₀			
1.0	1.0	5.0	0.61
1.0	2.0	5.0	0.63
1.0	4.0	5.0	0.64
1.0	6.0	5.0	0.60
1.0	10.0	5.0	0.60
Effect of varying [HClO ₄]			
1.0	2.0	2.0	0.41
1.0	2.0	5.0	0.61
1.0	2.0	10.0	0.85
1.0	2.0	20.0	1.53

At constant $[HClO_4]$ with several fold excess of the substrate (5–20 times), the plots of $1/[CAT]$ versus time were linear for two half-lives and the pseudo-second order rate constants were unaffected by the changes in $[CAT]_0$ (Table 1), establishing second order kinetics in $[CAT]$. In DCT oxidations the rate followed first order kinetics in $[DCT]$ and the first order plots were linear for two half-lives.

At constant $[oxidant]$ and $[SC]$ the rates increased with increase in $[HClO_4]$ in both the oxidations (Tables 1 and 2). Plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [HClO_4]$ were linear with slopes < 1 , while the rates were independent of $[SC]$ with both the oxidants. Plot of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ was linear with CAT while it attained the limiting value for DCT oxidation but the double reciprocal plot was linear with the latter.

TABLE 2—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR OXIDATION OF SEMICARBAZIDE (SC) BY DICHLORAMINE-T (DCT) IN 1 : 1 (v/v) WATER-METHANOL MEDIUM

Temp. = 303 K, $\mu = 0.30 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$			
[DCT] ₀ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$	[SC] ₀ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$	[HClO ₄] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$	k_{obs} $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Effect of varying [DCT] ₀			
0.25	1.0	1.0	7.6
0.5	1.0	1.0	7.1
1.0	1.0	1.0	7.1
2.0	1.0	1.0	7.4
Effect of varying [SC] ₀			
0.5	0.5	1.0	7.3
0.5	1.0	1.0	7.1
0.5	2.0	1.0	7.4
0.5	4.0	1.0	7.4
Effect of varying [HClO ₄]			
0.5	1.0	0.5	4.0
0.5	1.0	1.0	7.1
0.5	1.0	2.0	11.2
0.5	1.0	4.0	15.0

Increase in ionic strength of the medium slightly decreased the rate with CAT while it increased in DCT oxidations. Decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by increasing the methanol composition increased the rate with CAT, but it decreased the rate of DCT oxidations. Addition of the reduced product of oxidants, *p*-toluenesulphonamide had little effect in both cases, while addition of Cl^- had no effect (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF MEDIUM AND ADDITION OF REACTION PRODUCTS PTS AND CHLORIDE ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF SEMICARBAZIDE BY CAT AND DCT AT 303 K

Temp. = 303 K, $\mu = 0.3 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$		
μ $\text{mol } dm^{-3}$	k_{obs} ($dm^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} s^{-1}$) CAT	k_{obs} ($\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$) DCT
0.1	0.65	4.6
0.2	—	6.1
0.3	0.61	7.1
0.4	0.59	9.3
0.5	0.40	—
[PTS] ($\times 10^3 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$)		
1.0	—	7.0
2.0	0.62	6.4
4.0	0.62	5.9
6.0	0.58	—
8.0	—	5.7

(Table 3 contd.)

[Cl ⁻] ($\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³)		
2.0	0.62	7.3
4.0	0.62	7.6
8.0	0.61	—
10.0	0.58	7.6
Methanol (%)		
10	0.70	—
20	0.85	11.7
30	—	9.3
40	1.25	—
60	—	6.1

The rates were measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters were computed from the Arrhenius plots (Table 4).

TABLE 4—KINETIC AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF SEMICARBAZIDE BY CAT AND DCT

Order with respect to	CAT	DCT
[Oxidant]	2.0	1.0
[SC]	0.0	0.0
[H ⁺]	0.86	0.83
Activation parameters :		
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	88.0	48.6
log A	6.4	5.2
$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	35.5	46.1
$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-131.5	-153.1
$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	75.3	92.5

Chloramine-T (RNCINa, R = CH₂C₆H₄SO₂) and dichloramine-T (RNCl₂) are the sources of positive halogen species and hypohalites. They furnish different reactive species depending upon pH of the reaction medium. Equilibria (2) exist in their aqueous or partially aqueous solutions⁵,

$$(K_a \text{ of RNHCl} = 2.82 \times 10^{-5} \text{ at } 25^\circ)$$

Further protonation takes place under high acid conditions,

$$(K_d \text{ of RNHCl} = 0.058 \text{ at } 25^\circ)$$

$$(K_h \text{ of RNCl}_2 = 8.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ at } 25^\circ)$$

$$(K_b \text{ of RNHCl} = 4.88 \times 10^{-8} \text{ at } 25^\circ)$$

Therefore, the probable reactive species in the acid solutions of CAT and DCT are RNHCl, RNCl₂, HOCl at low [H⁺] and possibly RNH₂Cl⁺ and H₂OCl⁺ under high acid conditions.

Mechanism of oxidations :

(a) *With chloramine-T:* Kinetics of second order in [CAT], fractional order in [H⁺] and zero

order in [SC] may be explained by two-pathway mechanism (Schemes 1 and 2) as the plot of k_{obs} vs [H⁺] was linear with an intercept on the ordinate. Further the double reciprocal plot, $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ was non-linear (Fig. not shown).

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

The combined rate law is given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = K_1 k_2 [\text{CAT}]^2 + K_1 k_s [\text{CAT}]^2 [\text{H}^+] \quad (9)$$

where, $K_1 = K'_1 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $k_2 = k'_2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = K_1 \{k_2 + k_s [\text{H}^+]\} \quad (10)$$

The rate law (10) predicts linearity between k_{obs} and [H⁺] in conformity with the observed results.

With dichloramine-T: Oxidation of SC by DCT followed first order kinetics in [DCT], fractional order in [H⁺] and it was independent of [S]. Plot of k_{obs} vs [H⁺] was non-linear in this case attaining limiting value, while the double reciprocal plot, $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ was linear with finite intercept on the ordinate (Figs. not shown). These results may be explained by Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

Based on Scheme 3, rate laws (11–13) have been deduced,

$$-\frac{d[\text{DCT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_s k_s [\text{DCT}][\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_s [\text{H}^+]} \quad \text{where } k_s = k'_s [\text{H}_2\text{O}] \quad (11)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_4 k_5 [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_4 [\text{H}^+]} \quad (12)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{K_4 k_5 [\text{H}^+]} + \frac{1}{k_5} \quad (13)$$

The rate law (13) predicts linearity between $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ and $1/[\text{H}^+]$ in accordance with the observed results. The constants K_4 and k_5 were calculated from the slope and intercept of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ plot, and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}] = 55.56 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($K_4 = 49.2$, $k_5 = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

A detailed mechanism of oxidation of semicarbazide by the reactive species HOCl is given by Scheme 4.

The *N*-chloro intermediate formed by the interaction of the substrate with HOCl undergoes disproportionation with the elimination of HCl and then reacts with an additional molecule of HOCl to give the final products. Variations in rates of oxidations due to the changes in ionic strength or dielectric constant of the reaction medium may be explained by Amis¹⁰ and other theories¹¹. The formations

of more ordered activated complexes is evident from the negative values for the entropies of activation.

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